

TEACHERS' ENTREPRENEURIAL COMPETENCE AND TEACHING METHODS IN ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION: A BASIS FOR TEACHERS TRAINING CURRICULUM

Cris S. Saranza, MBA¹
Nina Lyn E. Bueno, PhD²
Glenn R. Andrin, PhD³
Melvin M. Niñal, PhD⁴

Graduate Studies and Professional Development, St. Paul University – Surigao, Philippines

Article history:	Abstract:
Received: 30 th March 2022 Accepted: 28 th April 2022 Published: 11 th June 2022	Entrepreneurship education is among the key drivers of the country's economy, and teachers are primarily responsible for its integration into teaching and finding the best and most useful method. The purpose of this research is to determine the level of entrepreneurial competence and teaching methods among entrepreneurship education teachers. Focusing on the concept of entrepreneurial competencies combining conceptual, human relations, strategic, commitment, opportunity, organizational and strategic competencies. Using quantitative – descriptive survey, the study tested its significant difference and relationship when grouped with the profile variables. The findings indicate a significant correlation between the variables particularly, with the technical competence which has the strongest correlation. The paper sheds some light concerning the status of the current entrepreneurial competence of the teachers in the division and recommends training curriculum to develop their competencies in handling the subject.

Keywords: conceptual, human relations, strategic, commitment, opportunity, organizational, strategic.

1. INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship plays a crucial role in the activities on nurturing economic growth and development, especially in developing countries like the Philippines. These activities are not only the drivers of technological innovation; they also provide employment opportunities and increase competitiveness.

Entrepreneurs are considered as the backbone of the country's economy (Capote, 2015). In fact, in the 2016 Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) Statistics of Department of Trade and Industry (DTI), MSMEs account for 99.57% of the total establishments, of which 89.63% were microenterprises. These indicate that MSMEs contributed almost 63.3% of the total jobs generated by all types of business establishments, contributing 35.7% of the total domestic sales volume. Thus, the need to develop and promote entrepreneurship and its education are relevant issues of the current interest in the country.

Entrepreneurship education is among the key drivers in the process of building a stronger culture of entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial mindsets (Pfeifer et al., 2016). It is one of the instruments that empower youth to be the creators instead of seekers of job. Entrepreneurship education helps students from all socioeconomic backgrounds, creates opportunities, ensures social justice, instills confidence, and stimulates the economy (Maresch, 2016).

For the longest period, the Philippines educational system has only ten (10) years of basic education compared to 12 or more years in other countries. Among ASEAN member nations, the Philippines is the only country with less than 12 years of pre-university education. The government has continuously addressed the challenge of access and quality in the Philippines through various initiatives such as the K to 12 programs. The K to 12 educational system is primarily 13 years of primary education from Kindergarten to Senior High School (SHS). The Department of Education (DepEd) reiterated that the K to 12 program aims to provide students ample time to master concepts and skills, develop life-long learners, and prepare SHS graduates for tertiary education, middle-level skills development, employment, and entrepreneurship (Department of Education, 2017). Entrepreneurship is an applied subject to teach and develop the students with needed competence to be an entrepreneur whatever track or strand they choose as an SHS student.

The fulfillment of this goal requires functioning implementation models and methods for entrepreneurship education, especially in Senior High School. The teachers are considered as the main player in the realization of the goals for entrepreneurship education. Therefore, the provision of suitable infrastructure, adequate resources, and qualified academic staff, innovation, and lifelong learning are central to its implementation. Since there are no definite

pedagogical guiding principle for entrepreneurship education, teachers are generally responsible for its integration into their teaching and, finding the best and most useful method. Teachers have found difficulties in getting relevant contents and methods to implement entrepreneurship education and thus in relation to the use of national and international strategies (Seikkula-Leino, 2008). Moreover in Deakins et al., (2005) and Draycott et al., (2011) researches, showed major attention being paid to learning results, and working methods of the teachers have been consequently ignored.

In addition, it is observed by the researcher that in Senior High School, specifically in Surigao del Norte Division, there are teachers handling entrepreneurship who do not have any background in business or did graduate in any business-related courses. It is also evident that very limited numbers of business teachers are being hired, which most of the time, are assigned to those schools offering Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM) strand.

Teachers cannot teach how to be entrepreneurial without themselves being entrepreneurial (European Commission June 2013). And so, the researcher felt the need to assess the entrepreneurial competence of teachers who are teaching entrepreneurship so that effective and successful implementation of entrepreneurship education program is achieved. The study's framework is anchored on the premises that if the educational system is to develop new breeds of entrepreneurs as the future economic movers, it is but appropriate that the learning sources or the educators should be well-equipped and sensitive to the needs of the learner. To do this, the level of entrepreneurial competence of teachers has assessed as well as the levels of teaching methods they used in teaching entrepreneurship.

1.1 Conceptual Framework of the Study

Entrepreneurs come from a wide range of backgrounds and age groups and have diverse experiences and skill sets. These entrepreneurial demographics are related to competencies, and the information is useful for prospective entrepreneurs seeking to learn more about how their backgrounds compare to successful entrepreneurs (Olien et al., 2013).

The study is anchored in the concept of Man and Lau, (2005) as cited by Kaushal (2016) and Baum et al., (2001) as cited by LI Xiang (2009). Seven major competency areas are identified in their work. First is the **conceptual**, the ability in making analytical and cognitive thinking, decision making and problem-solving, innovating, learning, and sustaining temporal tension in coping with uncertainty and risk belong to this category (McClelland, 1987; Bird, 1995). The **human relations** is another competency that relates to person-to-person or individual-to-group based interactions like creating a concept of cooperation and trust, using communication and interpersonal skill, contacts and connections, persuasive ability, (Man et al., 2002).

Next is the **technical** competency which entrepreneurs must understand the basic market knowledge, economic principles, and ethical practices and the fundamental processes and characteristics of entrepreneurship (Olien et al., 2013). Moreover, the **commitment** has a strong competency in totally committing, determining and dedicating, as well as taking proactive actions towards their responsibilities and duties. The **opportunity** category of competencies comprises of the entrepreneurial activities in spotting opportunities, actively seeking new opportunities, and developing the opportunities. Then the **organizational** ability to lead, control, monitor, organize, and develop the external and internal resources towards the firm's capabilities through the entrepreneur's organizing competencies in different areas. And the **strategic** competency that requires the entrepreneur to have a clear vision for their business, to have clear goals to achieve, or to formulate and implement strategies to achieve these vision and goals.

Moreover, the demographic profiles of the teachers are known to relate to the teaching methods affecting students' performance (Tshering, Gembo & Cox, 2017). Some researchers have pointed out that a particular feature of teaching skills is their interactive nature. Solomon (2007) stated that "educational institutions are moving towards more of knowledge-sharing role where class discussion and guest speakers are becoming more popular". Neck and Greene (2011) also added the engagement in a classroom discussion is different from a case study discussion. Accordingly, the active role of learners should be applied and built in the learning process of entrepreneurship education pedagogy, same as to the methods on non-traditional teaching (Gibb, 2011).

The entrepreneurial competence of teachers is related to the way they manage their classrooms through the use of effective teaching methods. According to Tschannen-Moran and Johnson (2011), the more teachers are immersed and engaged in the process of learning in a specific lesson or field, the better they can connect their students in the process of learning that field. It is supported on the findings of Pihie & Bagheri (2011), which provide a clearer picture on the relationship of entrepreneurial competence among technical and vocational secondary school teachers teaching and assessment practices in the classroom and their performance in the school system.

In the context of the study, the results of the profile of the respondents are used to determine its possible significant differences in the level of teachers' entrepreneurial competence and level of utilization of teaching methods. Furthermore, the study also identified the relationship between entrepreneurial competence and teaching method. The results of the study are used as the basis for creating a training curriculum for the teachers, as presented in the research paradigm in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Paradigm on Teachers’ Entrepreneurial Competence and Teaching Methods in Entrepreneurship Education

1.2 Statement of the Problem

This study is focused on the Level of Entrepreneurial Competence and Teaching Methods among teachers handling Entrepreneurship subject in Surigao del Norte Division. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents?
2. What is the level of entrepreneurial competence of teachers in teaching entrepreneurship?
3. What is the level of utilization of teaching methods used by the teachers in entrepreneurship education?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of entrepreneurial competence and teaching methods when grouped according to the profile variables?
5. Is there a significant relationship between entrepreneurial competence and teaching methods?
6. Based on the findings, what training interventions may be proposed to enhance the teachers’ competence and methods in teaching entrepreneurship?

The study is guided by three (3) null hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance.

H₁: There is no significant difference in the level of entrepreneurial competence when grouped according to the respondents' profile.

H₂: There is no significant difference in the level of utilization of teaching methods when grouped according to the respondents’ profile.

H₃: There is no significant relationship between entrepreneurial competence and teaching method.

1.3 Scope and Limitation of the Study

To facilitate the delimitation in understanding the intention and content of the study, parameters were specified. This study was focused on the teachers’ level of entrepreneurial competence and teaching methods in the Department of Education - Surigao del Norte Division. The study was conducted through an online survey questionnaire among four (4) clusters of the division. Only the public school teachers handling entrepreneurship subject in Senior High School were considered respondents of the study. The primary source of data was gathered from the answered survey questionnaires. On the other hand, the secondary source of data was taken from books, e-books, journals, and other online sources.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Entrepreneurship Education

The programs in entrepreneurship education are increasingly being established and expanded to develop students with competency and knowledge necessary to create economic value and jobs. It enables them to be responsible and business-minded individuals. It also helps people develop the skills, knowledge, and attitudes required to achieve the goals they set out for themselves (European Commission, 2018). Thus, the role of entrepreneurship education is a critical factor in producing potential entrepreneurs. However, according to Duval-Couetil (2013), though these programs create positive outcomes for students, the magnitude and scope of these outcomes have not been well explored in the literature.

According to Shane (2000) as cited by Gautam, Manish (2015), entrepreneurship education is a study of the source of opportunities and process of discovery in which an individual's creativity and risk-taking turn ideas into

action. On the other hand, Colette Henry, Frances Hill, Claire Leitch, (2005) said that though there is the increasing number of literature in that field, there is still considerable uncertainty in the entrepreneurship academy about whether individuals can be taught to be entrepreneurs. But on the narrative report of the European Commission (2011), entrepreneurship education is thus about life-wide as well as lifelong competence development.

Thus, it is essential to understand the definition, as this will affect the objective and the impact of the program. In this study, 'entrepreneurship education' is defined as the process of providing students with entrepreneurial skills and knowledge to be prepared in their entrepreneurial life.

Definitions of entrepreneurship education among scholars

Author/ Source	Definitions
Anderson & Jack (2008)	Entrepreneurial knowledge is the concept, skill, and mentality that individual business owners use.
Fayolle et al., (2006)	Consists of "any pedagogical [program] or process of education for entrepreneurial attitudes and skills."
Gibb (1993)	Several enterprising behaviors define entrepreneurship that is underpinned by specific skills and attributes.
Kourilsky (1995)	Entrepreneurial education is opportunity recognition, the marshaling of resources in the presence of risk, and building a business venture.
Mwasalwiba (2010)	Some educational process can affect attitudes, behaviors or intentions, acquisition of personal skills, business formation, opportunity recognition, and the management of small firms.
Pittaway & Cope (2007)	Educational aspects covered include employability skills, social enterprise, self-employment, venture creation, employment in small businesses, small business management, and, the management of high-growth ventures.

Teachers are mainly interested in individual-level competency in helping students become more skilled and motivated to start and succeed in the new endeavor (Bird, 2002). Thus, a common concern among academic institutions is to encourage students to become more business-inclined and more innovative. To achieve this goal in entrepreneurship education, one must instill in students the development of entrepreneurial competencies to better prepared for an entrepreneurial life. Knowing what entrepreneurial competencies need to develop is vital in trying to meet the training needs of people at each level of the entrepreneurial process.

2.1.1 Entrepreneurship Education in the Philippines

In the Philippines, the under Republic Act (RA) No. 7722, Memorandum Order No. 17 Series of 2005 indicating the Curriculum Requirement for Bachelor of Science in Entrepreneurship has pushed the formal integration of entrepreneurship education by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED). These contain the new academic and developmental thrusts of the Entrepreneurship Programs and Courses in the Tertiary Level. There is an increase in colleges and universities offering business and entrepreneurship courses integrating entrepreneurship in their schools, as a full four-year course leading to a degree, a track, or as an essential subject.

According to Gatchalian (2010), there are intensive efforts in the government and the private sector to progress entrepreneurship education as a long-term solution to economic advancement. Anticipating the future offering of the course on entrepreneurship will increase, and programs will take on a newer form as it grows and develops over time.

On the other hand, Velasco (2013) pointed out that entrepreneurship education in the Philippines heavily focuses on the development of entrepreneurs in terms of encouraging start-ups. There is a lack of focus in developing creativity and innovation as a mindset of the student in the formal education system. There is also minimal support from the academe and industry to aid emerging entrepreneurial undertaking to grow and sustain the business.

In a case study conducted by Rauh-Bier (2016) in the Philippines, results indicated that although the population as highly literate, and a majority of the entrepreneurs finished secondary or college education, the training, and entrepreneurial capacity development have not been given much attention in formal education. In most part, the school remains focused on training students to be employees. While these are essential qualities, there is no indication in the preparation to face entrepreneurial challenges in the local context. They lack practice at entrepreneurial know-how, problem-solving, or imagination.

Students need entrepreneurial competencies to be effective in their field of work, and so, entrepreneurship education must be taught and directed with the right teaching method by to inculcate the right expertise and attitude to the students. Entrepreneurial competence and knowledge in business management is an essential factor of success in the entrepreneurial endeavor. Therefore, teachers should also possess these competencies since they are to teach entrepreneurship (Capote and Vedula-Dinagsao, 2015).

Salamanca (2009) provides a clear description of the role of the teacher in the business of education, pointing out that continuing professional development is necessary for this profession. Competence, ideal qualities, and values are essential to develop and acquire effective teaching methods and techniques. The teachers deserve to be elevated

at the center stage of any educational endeavor because they provide the much-needed direction, guidance, and energy throughout the teaching/learning informative episode.

2.2 Entrepreneurial Competence

Competency refers to the cluster of observable and measurable knowledge, skills, abilities, and personal attributes that enable and encourage an individual or an organization to act efficiently in a job. The new Oxford dictionary defines competency as the power, knowledge, capability to do a task, whereas according to Merriam Webster competency is the sufficiency of means for the necessities and conveniences of life. Oxford further states that competence and skill used as synonyms. It means that competency is a broader concept and helps a person to do better in practical form assists transformation of knowledge, skills, and attitudes to perform successfully in a particular task and hence helps to distinguish between a superior and other performers.

Entrepreneurial competencies are defined as essential characteristics by an individual, which result in new venture creation, survival, and growth (Mitchelmore & Rowley, 2010). Entrepreneurial competencies consider as a higher level characteristic covering the knowledge, personality traits, and skills that can be evident as the total ability to perform a job role successfully which enable entrepreneurs to achieve and maintain business success (Man et al., 2002). It is through various implications that it is tried to adjust comprehension of entrepreneurial competencies for achieving performance results. The definition of competency is the aggregate limit of the entrepreneur to perform the proficient job effectively (Kausal, 2016). According to Man and Lau (2005), the entrepreneurs' competencies are associated with their characteristics and performance at a company level. The authors proposed six areas of entrepreneurial competency, namely, commitment, conceptual, human relations, opportunity, organizational, and strategic competencies. Thus, this framework has been referred to in the present research to address entrepreneurial competencies.

2.2.1. Conceptual Competency

Conceptual capabilities express to a kind of competencies which are not effectively identifiable behavior but rather are frequently viewed as imperative for entrepreneurial achievement. The capacity in making cognitive and analytical reasoning, learning, decision making and problem-solving, continuing temporal strain, innovating and in adapting to uncertainty and risk is covered by this kind (McClelland, 1987; Bird, 1995). They have a more grounded linkage with entrepreneurial attributes and are less directly noticeable. They include a high level of conceptual exercises and are reflected in the entrepreneur's methods when they conduct analysis, learn, make decisions, and tackle issues, and so forth. They may likewise improve the viability of conveying an assignment in the present or the future. Like strategic competencies, it requires a more abstract level of abilities. But, in contrast to strategic competencies, conceptual competencies are concerned about a shorter-term point of view, settling immediate activities, or requiring instinctive reactions (Man et al., 2002).

2.2.2. Human Relations Competency

This type of competency relates to person-to-person or individual-to-group based interactions, like building a sense of cooperation and trust, using connections, persuasion ability, communication and interpersonal skill (Man et al., 2002). Successful entrepreneurs need to acquire competencies in relationship building, communication, persuasive, and interpersonal abilities (McClelland, 1987). According to Bird (1995), as cited by LI, Xiang (2009), this relationship building activities as entrepreneurial bonding, which contains not only the development of a relationship but also the reformation of relationships as the company matures or a partnership is dissolved.

2.2.3. Technical Competency

Entrepreneurial education stands toward the acquisition of technical knowledge from a new field or adding up to the existing one. Rae & Carswell, (2000) as cited by Kissi (2015) added that better understanding of entrepreneurship knowledge is crucial in the creation and development of entrepreneurship education and training programs to determine the entrepreneur's learning needs via concentrating on the personal and business development of the entrepreneur. It was supported by Ahmad et al., (2014) saying that one of the significant factors that have been revealed as having a substantial impact on entrepreneurial success is the technical knowledge and "know-how."

Entrepreneurship technical competency, as described by CareerOneStop (2010), has seven competency items: (1) Principles of Entrepreneurship: Characteristics and knowledge of processes that is fundamental to entrepreneurial undertakings; (2) Innovation & Invention: Formulating new ideas for and applications of processes and products; (3) Planning: Organizational goal determination and strategy identification to achieve that goal; (4) Marketing: Planning and implementing a strategy in promoting and selling products, services and ideas; (5) Financial Management: Money and other assets management and control, to effectively and efficiently complete entrepreneurial activities; (6) Business Operations: Managing functions in involved ongoing activities in relation to the running of a business; and (7) Risk Assessment and Management: Knowledge of company's and competing product lines and the methods to display them.

2.2.4. Commitment Competency

Successful entrepreneurs are often considered as a hardworking individual with a restless attitude in their job. Meaning to say, they have a strong competency in totally obligating, determining and devoting, as well as taking proactive steps towards their responsibilities and duties. This relates to the entrepreneurial role of the drive to see firm through to realization applied by Chandler and Jansen (1992) as cited by Kausal (2016). Another facet of this competency is the initiative or proactive direction, which calls for the entrepreneurs having a sense of urgency in taking actions before being asked or forced to by events (McClelland, 1987). To sum up, commitment competencies are those motivation the entrepreneur to move forward with the business.

2.2.5. Opportunity Competency

The most distinctive competencies for the entrepreneur are the opportunity-related competency. It was author McClelland (1987) who finds "to see and act on opportunities" as one of the competencies for successful entrepreneurs. The unique entrepreneurial roles) are the capacity to perceive and anticipate, taking advantage of opportunities (Chandler and Jansen, 1992). Consequently, this type incorporates entrepreneurial activities in term of spotting opportunities; effectively look for new opportunities, and creating opportunities.

2.2.6. Organizational Competency

Another group of competencies is organizing competencies. As indicated by McClelland's (1987) efficiency orientation", "concern for a high quality of work," and "monitoring" ought to be the required competencies in overseeing different functional areas in a firm to keep the firm working proficiently. Besides, Chandler and Jansen (1992) recommended the significance of managerial roles of an entrepreneur in human competence. Generally, organizing competencies are similar to the managerial competencies as noted by Boyatzis, (1982). These competencies require the capacity to lead, control, monitor, organize, and develop the external and internal assets towards the company's abilities through the entrepreneurs' organizing competencies in various areas.

2.2.7. Strategic Competency

As an owner of the firm, the entrepreneur must set the direction for the entire organization. This type of competencies requires the entrepreneur to have a conceptual ability or vision of their business, to have clear objectives to accomplish, or to define and execute strategies to achieve these objectives, for or example, McClelland's (1987) systematic planning, and Lau et al. 's (2000) strategic planning competencies. Generally, these competencies are identified with a setting, assessing and executing the strategies of the firm, while calling for abilities and skills from a more broad and long-term perspective.

2.3 Teaching Methods in Entrepreneurship Education

In the study of Lonappan et al (2011) as cited by Arasti et al., (2016), teaching methods are categorized into following: action learning, case study, group discussion, group project, guest speakers, individual presentation, individual written report, formal lectures, seminar, video recorded, web-based learning. Also, Solomon et al., (2002) as cited by Babatunji & Mohammad (2018) emphasized that the most common and popular teaching methods in entrepreneurship education are creation and development of business plans, case studies, and lectures.

On the other hand, Hytti and O'Gorman (2004), as cited by Fatoki (2014), argue that offering entrepreneurship education depends on its objectives. If it targets to expand the comprehension of what entrepreneurship is about, the most ideal approach to achieve it is to give data through open or public channels such as lectures, seminars, and use of media. In any case, if the goal is to furnish people with entrepreneurial competencies at apply legitimately to work, the most ideal path is to give specialized or technical instruction that empower them to be straightforwardly engage entrepreneurial process. Lastly, if the goal is to make them to go about as entrepreneurs through encouraging examinations by doing entrepreneurship out in a controlled domain or environment through role-playing or simulation activity (Ahmad et al., 2004).

According to Mwasalwiba (2010) and Tasnim (2012), the teaching methods for entrepreneurship characterized into two, the traditional methods and non-traditional methods. The former, also known as passive methods comprise of business plan, project works, reading, regular lectures, and seminars. However, the latter also known as active methods are more action-based. It seeks to improve students' analytic and creative way of critical thinking technique anticipates that the educator should encourage learning and apply strategies that empower students' self-discovery, which may incorporate computer-generated simulations on new business decision-making and build-up their skills in multifaceted decision-making. Other non-traditional teaching methods include attachments and visits to public and private companies to acquire hands-on experience (Balan, 2014).

The three most common methods are lectures, case studies, group discussions (Arasti et al., 2016). These are similar methods utilized in different business-related courses, which, as indicated by Bennett (2006) are detached and less viable in impacting entrepreneurial attributes. Fiet (2000) clarifies that educators depend on lecture-based methods since they can be effectively practiced, and furthermore on the grounds that they require less investment. Other methods utilized, yet not as regular as the previous group, include: business/computer or game simulations, video and filming, role models or guest speakers, business plan creation, project works. Additionally employed were

recreational competitions and games, presentations, real scenario small business endeavors, study visits and workshops. Mwasalwiba (2010) termed this category as "active" and is said to be progressively suitable for nurturing entrepreneurial attributes among participants.

In the Philippines, the study of Capote and Vedula-Dinagsao (2015), most of the methods used in entrepreneurship education are only those that are found inside the classroom. Teachers should also use teaching methods outside the classroom, such as field trips and exposure to the real business world, training and or seminar about teaching methods that promote interactive learning in entrepreneurship education.

Based on the previous studies above, it suggests that economic progress is possible by inculcating an entrepreneurial mindset through entrepreneurship education, in which the teachers play a crucial role. Hence it is not surprising that loads of frameworks and lists of entrepreneurial competencies have been developed. As the statement suggested, entrepreneurial understanding competency is an essential factor in entrepreneurship education so as its methods in teaching the subject.

3. METHOD

3.1 Research Design

In this study, quantitative research design, descriptive survey was used to determine the level of entrepreneurial competence and teaching methods. According to Calderon (2008), as cited by Alberto et al., (2011), the descriptive method is used for frequencies, averages, and other statistical calculations. It involves the description of data and characteristics, so as the analysis, and interpretation of the present nature of population or phenomena. Most of the time, conducting a survey is the best approach prior to writing descriptive research. This method was used to gather information to test the hypothesis or to answer questions concerning the current status of the subject of the study.

3.2 Sampling Technique

The study used a non-probability, purposive sampling. It was purposive sampling because only the teachers handling entrepreneurship subject in Senior High School in Surigao del Norte division were considered as the respondents of the study. Purposive sampling is a form of non-probability sampling in which decisions are based upon a variety of criteria including the knowledge of the research issue, or capacity and willingness to participate in the research, concerning the individuals to be included in the sample are taken by the researcher (Oliver, 2006).

3.3 Research Instrument

A researcher-made and adapted questionnaire were used to determine entrepreneurial competence based on the competencies identified by Man et al. (2005). An adapted questionnaire on personal entrepreneurial competency from the University of the Philippines Institute for Small Scale Industries (UP-SSI) was utilized. This composed of three (3) parts and the first part determined the teacher-respondents demographic profile. Second part identified the level of entrepreneurial competence of teacher-respondents in terms of opportunity, conceptual, organization, strategic, commitment, and relationship following the present model identified by the Man (2001). It was selected due to its comprehensiveness, validity, and reliability. Besides the competencies identified by the previous studies such as McClelland (1978), Chandler and Jansen (1992), Baum et al., (2001), Bird (1995), etc. are fully covered by the competencies. And the third part included the levels of utilization of teaching methods in entrepreneurship education is examined thru a list of working methods enumerated to get an overview of how often teacher-respondent used these methods and working methods to carry out entrepreneurship education in their work. The list of working methods are derived from combined literature of Lonappan et al.,(2011), Solomon et al., (2002), Hytti & O'Gorman (2004), Ahmad et al., (2004), Mwasalwiba (2010) and Tasnim (2012).

3.4 Validity and Reliability Test

After completion of the pilot survey, the data were analyzed using SPSS. Before the distribution of the questionnaires, the draft was initially submitted to the adviser and experts and also to the typical respondent for face and content validity. Reliability refers to an assessment tool's degree in producing a consistent and stable result. The study resulted in 0.851 Cronbach alpha, indicating that the instrument was reliable. Commonly, Cronbach alpha is used to measure the internal consistency; that is, how closely related a set of items are as a group. It is most commonly used when a Likert type scale is adopted in the questionnaire to determine whether the scale is reliable or not. The study used the suggested values above 0.6 coefficient value (Hair, Black, Babin, & Anderson, 2010).

3.5 Data Gathering and Analysis

A letter of approval to the Schools Division Superintendent, to administer the questionnaires was secured from the Division Office of Surigao del Norte. A letter to the school principals/heads along with the photocopied letter of approval from the division office was accomplished asking permission to allow the teachers handling entrepreneurship in Senior High School to participate in the study. The survey questionnaires were personally handed over or emailed to the participants along with the letter of request to answer the questionnaire. To ensure the proper accomplishment of the questionnaire, the researcher explained the purpose of the study to the respondents. The data

gathered were classified, tabulated, and analyzed to answer the statements of the problem. The frequency count and percentage distribution was used to represent the average rating as to the profile of the teacher-respondents. Then the mean and standard deviation was applied to determine the level of teachers' entrepreneurial competence and teaching methods. To determine the significant difference in the level of entrepreneurial competence of the teacher-respondents and level of teaching methods when they are grouped according to the profile variables, the analysis of variance was utilized. Finally, Pearson moment correlation was employed to determine the significant relationship between the level of teachers' competence and level of teaching methods.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Problem 1: What is the demographics of the respondents?

Table 1 - Profile of the Teacher-Respondents

Profile Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
22 – 28 years old	10	29
29 – 35 years old	14	41
36 – 42 years old	6	18
43 – 50 years old	4	12
Sex		
Male	10	29
Female	24	71
Majoring Course		
Undergraduate Course		
Business-Related	15	44
Secondary Education	16	47
Others	3	9
Graduate Studies Course		
MAEM	2	6
Master in Industrial Engineering	3	9
MBA	3	9
MPA	1	3
None	25	73
Years in Teaching		
0 – 6 years	27	79
7 – 13 years	4	12
14 – 20 years	1	3
21 – 27 years	2	6
Years in Teaching Entrepreneurship		
0 – 2 years	27	79
3 – 5 years	4	12
6 – 8 years	2	6
9 – 11 years	1	3
Family Business		
Yes	18	53
No	16	47
Years in Family Business (n=18)		
1 – 12 years	12	66
13 – 24 years	4	22
25 – 36 years	1	6
37 – 48 years	1	6
Participated or experienced in creating new business		
Yes	14	41
No	20	59
The entrepreneurial program course experience		
Yes	5	15
No	29	85
Entrepreneurial program course attended (n=5)		
Home economics	2	40
Food technology	1	20
Online Marketing	1	20
Poultry Farming cum Egg Production	1	20

Prior Entrepreneurship Training		
Yes	13	38
No	21	62
Prior Entrepreneurship Training Attended (n=13)		
Capability Building in Establishing General Merchandising Store	1	8
DTI sponsored Business Starters	1	8
Entrepreneurship Training for SHS Teachers	11	84

As indicated in Table 1, it shows that the majority of teachers handling entrepreneurship subject are female with about 71% and aged from 29 – 35 years old or 41%. More than half of them are secondary education and not business-related courses graduate, 47% and 9% respectively. Also, 73% of the respondents have not yet taken any graduate courses or studies. It is also indicated that most of the teachers are new in the teaching profession meaning with 0 – 6 years of experience or 79% and with 0 – 2 years in teaching the subject about 79%. However, 53% of the respondents have a family business for 1 – 12 years of experience or about 66%.

On the contrary, more than half of them (59%) have not participated or experienced creating a new business venture. Also, most of them have not taken any entrepreneurship program course (85%) and training (62%). The results imply that majority of the respondents have limited background, experience, and training on entrepreneurship or any business-related courses.

Problem 2: What is the level of entrepreneurial competence of teachers in teaching entrepreneurship?

Table 2 displays the level of entrepreneurial conceptual competence of teachers in teaching entrepreneurship. The highest mean response of 3.65 with a standard deviation of 0.49 and 0.65 respectively, demonstrated that the teachers prefer situations which they can control the outcomes as much as possible and find ways to complete tasks faster at work and home, and is interpreted as "very high competence." In contrast, the least mean response of 3.06 with a standard deviation of 0.65 revealed that some of the teachers refrain from doing risky things, interpreted as "high competence." As a result, the overall mean of 3.41, described as "strongly agree" shows that conceptual competency of the teachers is interpreted as "very high competence." This means that they have a very high ability to integrate information and make judgments based on relevant factors. The ability to think critically is essential to success in the world of business. It is relative to the statement of Constantine (2017), which states that learning entrepreneurship opens students to various opportunities to learn how to think critically and analyze the pieces on the board. Being aware of all the relevant factors and understanding how they affect each other is the foundation of a sound decision-making process.

Table 2 - Level of Entrepreneurial Competence of Teachers in Teaching Entrepreneurship in terms of Conceptual Competence

Item Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation
1. I prefer situations in which I can control the outcomes as much as possible.	3.65	0.49	Strongly Agree	Very High Competence
2. I do find ways to complete tasks faster at work and home.	3.65	0.65	Strongly Agree	Very High Competence
3. I weigh my chances of succeeding or failing before I decide to do something.	3.62	0.60	Strongly Agree	Very High Competence
4. I do things that are risky.	3.06	0.65	Agree	High Competence
5. I am never entirely happy with the way in which things are done; I always think there must be a better way.	3.09	0.57	Agree	High Competence
Grand Mean	3.41	0.59	Strongly Agree	Very High Competence

Table 3 shows the human relations entrepreneurial competence level of teachers in teaching entrepreneurship. Among the rating statements, getting important people to help in accomplishing goals has the highest mean response of 3.62 with a standard deviation of 0.60 and is interpreted as "very high competence" level. However, thinking of solutions that benefit everyone involved in the problem to reach their goals has the lowest mean response of 3.09 and a standard deviation of 0.62, which is interpreted as a "high competence" level. Thus, the variable's overall mean of 3.26, described as "strongly agree" with a standard deviation of 0.57, interpreted as "very high" human relation competence level. This means that the teacher-respondents has a very high relation with or between people, particularly in a workplace or professional setting. Human relations provides help in the workplace and as a result, assists in achieving career success. In the modern business world, teams are used to accomplish

company goals because teamwork includes people with a variety of skills. As supported by Dias (2012), in most businesses, to be successful at the job, need to depend on others. The importance of human relations is apparent because if people are not able to get along, have strong inter-relationships, and resolve conflicts, the organization as a whole will be less productive, which could affect profitability.

Table 3 - Level of Entrepreneurial Competence of Teachers in Teaching Entrepreneurship in terms of Human Relations Competence

Item Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation
1. I get others to support my recommendations.	3.15	0.36	Agree	High Competence
2. I do not spend much time thinking about how to influence others.	3.21	0.84	Agree	High Competence
3. I get important people to help me accomplish my goals.	3.62	0.60	Strongly Agree	Very High Competence
4. In order to reach my goals, I think of solutions that benefit everyone involved in the problem.	3.09	0.62	Agree	High Competence
5. I am able to get people who have strong opinions or ideas to change their minds.	3.24	0.43	Agree	High Competence
Grand Mean	3.26	0.57	Strongly Agree	Very High Competence

Table 4 shows the technical level of entrepreneurial competence among the respondents. Carrying out ongoing activities involving running a business has the highest mean of 3.41 with a standard deviation of 0.50, interpreted as "very high" level of technical competence. Most of the respondents do not know how to create business plans or feasibility studies with the mean response of 2.26 and a standard deviation of 0.86, interpreted as "low competence" level. And so, the technical level has an overall mean of 2.89 with a standard deviation of 0.60, described as "agree" and interpreted as "high competence" level. This means that though the technical level is high, it is still not enough. In fact, according to one of the respondents, "teaching entrepreneurship course is never easy, especially if one has no background of business management degree or any business relates courses". Technical competence describes the application of knowledge and skills needed to perform effectively in a specific role. It is closely aligned with the knowledge and skills needed for successful performance. According to Deba et al., (2014), to effectively teach the subject, one should demonstrate knowledge of subject matter content and skills and interrelates ideas and information within and across subject matter areas.

Table 4 - Level of Entrepreneurial Competence of Teachers in Teaching Entrepreneurship in terms of Technical Competence

Item Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation
1. I know how to create business plans or feasibility studies.	2.26	0.86	Disagree	Very High Competence
2. I can determine the best way of conducting market analysis to promote and sell products, services, and ideas.	2.62	0.74	Agree	High Competence
3. I have the knowledge of processes and characteristics that is central to entrepreneurial activities.	2.94	0.42	Agree	High Competence
4. I can carry out ongoing activities involving running a business.	3.41	0.50	Strongly Agree	Very High Competence
5. I can determine the direction of an organization and identify a strategy to achieve that direction.	3.21	0.48	Agree	High Competence
Grand Mean	2.89	0.60	Agree	High Competence

Table 5 presents the commitment level of entrepreneurial competence among the teacher-respondents. As shown above, being happy to do someone else's work to get the job done on time resulted to a "very high competence" interpretation and has the highest mean response of 3.71 and standard deviation of 0.46. On the other hand, keeping the promises has the lowest mean of 2.91 with a standard deviation of 0.83, interpreted as "high competence." Nonetheless, the variable is still rated "strongly agree" and is interpreted as "very high" level of commitment competence with an overall mean of 3.47, the standard deviation of 0.61. This means that most of the respondents have a strong commitment in their work, in fact, comments from the respondents show strong willingness to perform their assigned tasks efficiently provided that the school will also help them through the provision of training for them to be more effective in their job. An entrepreneur always delivers his promise promptly,

and he values his reputation. Dao-anes (2015) added that they are expected to set a high but realistic standard of excellence among themselves. It is supported by Cox (2018) that an effective educator needs to be committed and passionate not only to their students but to the teaching profession itself. This means abiding by the rules and regulations, embracing the principles of the teaching profession, as well as the requirements.

Table 5 - Level of Entrepreneurial Competence of Teachers in Teaching Entrepreneurship in terms of Commitment Competence

Item Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation
1. I know how to create business plans or feasibility studies.	2.26	0.86	Disagree	Very High Competence
2. I can determine the best way of conducting market analysis to promote and sell products, services, and ideas.	2.62	0.74	Agree	High Competence
3. I have the knowledge of processes and characteristics that is central to entrepreneurial activities.	2.94	0.42	Agree	High Competence
4. I can carry out ongoing activities involving running a business.	3.41	0.50	Strongly Agree	Very High Competence
5. I can determine the direction of an organization and identify a strategy to achieve that direction.	3.21	0.48	Agree	High Competence
Grand Mean	2.89	0.60	Agree	High Competence

Table 6 shows the level of entrepreneurial competence of teachers in terms of opportunity. It shows that most of the respondents, like challenges and new opportunities, has the highest mean response of 3.62 and a standard deviation of 0.49, interpreted as "very high competence" level. On the contrary, some of them are not up to trying things that are very new and different from what have done before, has the lowest mean of 3.18, a standard deviation of 0.80, interpreted as "high competence." Generally, majority of the respondents have a "very high" level of opportunity competence, based on the overall mean of 3.41 and a standard deviation of 0.58, which is described as "strongly agree." This means that the respondents have a high urge for situations which make it possible to do something that they want to do, have to do, or the possibility of doing something. Opportunity recognition has always been regarded as a primary aspect of entrepreneurship. Opportunity seeking is being active in finding openings in the environment which can be used in different ways to start a business, to create a new market or to improve business operations. Furthermore, opportunity seeking is what enables an entrepreneur to act and grab new business opportunities, even in the most problematic and hopeless situations (Alusen, 2016).

Table 6 - Level of Entrepreneurial Competence of Teachers in Teaching Entrepreneurship in terms of Opportunity Competence

Item Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation
1. I look for things that need to be done.	3.35	0.49	Strongly Agree	Very High Competence
2. I do things that need to be done before being asked to do so by others.	3.44	0.61	Strongly Agree	Very High Competence
3. I like challenges and new opportunities.	3.62	0.49	Strongly Agree	Very High Competence
4. I prefer activities that I know well and with which I am comfortable.	3.47	0.51	Strongly Agree	Very High Competence
5. I try things that are very new and different from what I have done before.	3.18	0.80	Agree	High Competence
Grand Mean	3.41	0.58	Strongly Agree	Very High Competence

In table 7, the organizational level of entrepreneurial competence among teachers is shown. The statement on planning a large project by breaking it down to smaller tasks receives the highest mean response of 3.65 with a standard deviation of 0.49 and is interpreted as "very high competence" level. But, thinking about the advantages and disadvantages of different ways of accomplishing things got the lowest mean of 2.82, a standard deviation of 0.76, but still interpreted as a "high competence" level. As a result, the organizational level of entrepreneurial competence is "very high competence" as described as "strongly agree" with an overall mean of 3.36 and a standard deviation of 0.65. This means that most of the respondents can structure their work and prepare their areas of responsibility. Organizational competencies are some of the most important and transferable job competence. It contains a set of

competences that support a person to plan, set priorities, and achieve goals. Besides, keeping the work organized enables the workers to focus on different tasks without getting mixed-up or lost, thus increasing efficiency and productivity in the place of work (Doyle, 2019).

Table 7 - Level of Entrepreneurial Competence of Teachers in Teaching Entrepreneurship in terms of Organizational Competence

Item Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation
1. I plan a large project by breaking it down into smaller tasks.	3.65	0.49	Strongly Agree	Very High Competence
2. I think about the advantages and disadvantages of different ways of accomplishing things.	2.82	0.76	Agree	High Competence
3. I try to think of all the problems I may encounter and plan what to do if each problem occurs.	3.56	0.66	Strongly Agree	Very High Competence
4. I deal with problems as they arise rather than spend time to anticipate them.	3.53	0.51	Strongly Agree	Very High Competence
5. If one approach to a problem does not work, I think of another approach.	3.24	0.82	Agree	High Competence
Grand Mean	3.36	0.65	Strongly Agree	Very High Competence

Table 8 shows the strategic level of entrepreneurial competence of the respondents. As indicated, the concern of meeting weekly goals as with yearly goals has the highest mean of 3.44, standard deviation 0.75, which is interpreted as "very high competence" level. However, having a clear plan in life has the lowest mean response of 3.06 and a standard deviation of 0.89, interpreted as a "high competence" level. The overall strategic competence level of the respondents has a mean of 3.25, a standard deviation of 0.84, described as "strongly agree" and is interpreted as "very high competence" level. This means that majority of the respondents have a reliable identification of long-term aims, interest, and means in achieving their goals. Strategic competence explains how people assess, create, foresee and think about the future for themselves and others. Bradford (2019), stated that it is an effective and valuable tool. Through developing a complete set of critical skills, one can apply of being strategic to come up sound decisions that can be associated to work or personal life.

Table 8 - Level of Entrepreneurial Competence of Teachers in Teaching Entrepreneurship in terms of Strategic Competence

Item Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation
1. I like to think about the future.	3.38	0.78	Strongly Agree	Very High Competence
2. It is a waste of time to worry about what to do with your life.	3.24	0.92	Agree	High Competence
3. The more specific I can be about what I want out of life, the more chance I have to succeed.	3.12	0.88	Agree	High Competence
4. I have a very clear plan for my life.	3.06	0.89	Agree	High Competence
5. I am as concerned about meeting my weekly goals as I am for my yearly goals.	3.44	0.75	Strongly Agree	Very High Competence
Grand Mean	3.25	0.84	Strongly Agree	Very High Competence

To summarize, it is revealed that among seven (7) variables measured, six (6) variables denote majority of the responses established that respondents "strongly agree" which is interpreted as "very high competence" level. However, the technical variable shows that the respondents only "agree" at this level, which corresponds to a "high competence" level only. In general, mean results portray 3.29, which displays "strongly agree" and considers as "very high" entrepreneurial competence level.

Problem 3: What is the level of utilization of teaching methods used by the teachers in entrepreneurship education?

Table 10 presents the level of utilization of teaching methods in entrepreneurship education. As indicated, the small business attachment and mentoring has the highest mean response of 3.47 with SD of 0.86, interpreted as "very high utilization". This means the majority of the teachers handling the subject are partnering with business

organizations in their locality. This may be because schools are required to partner with other organizations or stakeholders for curriculum implementation. However, conducting site visits or business establishment tours has the lowest mean of 1.85, a standard deviation of 1.18 and interpreted as sometimes. According to one of the respondents, financial constraint is one of the reasons why this method is not used. This is supported by the "No Collection Policy" as mandated by the Department of Education, and no budget allocation in classroom activities. As a result, the overall mean of 2.94 with a standard deviation of 1.09 is described as "often" and interpreted as "high" level only of utilization.

Table 9 - Level of Utilization of Teaching Methods

Teaching Methods	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Small Businesses Attachment and Mentoring	3.47	0.86	Always	Very High Utilization
2. Using PowerPoint Presentations in Discussions	3.29	0.91	Always	Very High Utilization
3. Facilitating Group Discussion on business concepts and issues	3.29	0.91	Always	Very High Utilization
4. Conducting Traditional Lectures	3.29	0.87	Always	Very High Utilization
5. Making Group Assignments and Projects on entrepreneurship topics	3.29	0.87	Always	Very High Utilization
6. Problem-Oriented Learning / Problem-Solving Activities	3.15	1.10	Often	High Utilization
7. Inviting Guest Speakers and Role Models	2.15	1.10	Often	High Utilization
8. Assigning Individual Assignments and Projects on entrepreneurship activities	3.12	1.01	Often	High Utilization
9. Using Case Studies on business issues or any specialized topics	3.12	1.01	Often	High Utilization
10. Interviewing with entrepreneurs	3.06	1.13	Often	High Utilization
11. Developing new venture creation projects	3.06	1.13	Often	High Utilization
12. Conducting Business Simulation Activities	3.00	1.21	Often	High Utilization
13. Conducting Research Project on business opportunities or any specialized topic	2.97	1.09	Often	High Utilization
14. Inviting young entrepreneurs to guide through support missions to help in their projects	2.97	1.09	Often	High Utilization
15. Role-playing on business-related scenarios	2.88	1.09	Often	High Utilization
16. Creating Business Plans	2.74	1.24	Often	High Utilization
17. Training in an enterprise	2.41	1.28	Sometimes	Low Utilization
18. Video Watching and Recording on Entrepreneurial Opportunities	2.38	1.23	Sometimes	Low Utilization
19. Conducting Seminars and Training on specialized lessons	2.29	1.09	Sometimes	Low Utilization
20. Site Visiting or Tour Business Establishments	1.85	1.18	Sometimes	Low Utilization
Grand Mean	2.94	1.07	Often	High Utilization

In the Philippines, entrepreneurship education is characterized by the development of entrepreneurs through business start-ups, but the sad reality is, there is less emphasis on creativity and innovation among students' mindset in higher education institutions. Moreover, there is less support from academic institutions and industries to budding entrepreneurs to start and sustain business ventures (Velasco, 2013). Besides, the professional development of entrepreneurship educators, however, is not as institutionalized. Even teaching information and resources are not well-known or are not available and accessible in many schools, thus, making it difficult for aspiring entrepreneurs to find the sources they need (Gatchalian, 2015). Teaching students to be entrepreneurial needs a different set of skills, insights, or sensitivity and teaching approaches and methods to connect, engage, and to motivate them.

Problem 4.1: Is there a significant difference in the level of entrepreneurial competence when grouped according to the profile variables?

As shown in table 10 of the ANOVA result. It can be gleaned that there is a significant difference in conceptual level as to the family business background with a p-value at 0.01, perhaps being exposed in a family business develops an ability to identify patterns between different situations that are not obviously and usually related, and to identify the underlying issues in complicated cases. There is also a significant difference in conceptual

competence as to entrepreneurial training with a p-value at 0.035 because attending training on entrepreneurship and networking with people, discussing business scenarios gain a better understanding of the matter.

Table 10 - ANOVA Result on Conceptual Entrepreneurial Competence

Dependent Variable	Grouping/Independent Variable	SS	MS	F	p-value	Decision
Conceptual Competence	Age	4.790	0.299	1.383	0.257	Accept H_1
	Sex	0.012	0.012	0.046	0.831	Accept H_1
	Years in teaching	2.762	0.307	1.290	0.292	Accept H_1
	Family business background	2.359	2.359	12.355	0.001	Reject H_1
	Entrepreneurial experience	0.118	0.118	0.451	0.507	Accept H_1
	Entrepreneurial education	0.755	0.755	3.131	0.086	Accept H_1
	Entrepreneurial training	1.116	1.116	4.857	0.035	Reject H_1

According to Kulkarni (2015), conceptual skill involves the ability to see the enterprise as a whole. To develop it, one must carefully observe entrepreneurs on how they analyze any situation and take actions and attend seminars and training on business management within or outside the industry.

Table 11 - ANOVA Result on Human Relations Entrepreneurial Competence

Dependent Variable	Grouping/Independent Variable	SS	MS	F	p-value	Decision
Human Relations Competence	Age	3.264	0.204	0.914	0.570	Accept H_1
	Sex	0.000	0.000	0.002	0.963	Accept H_1
	Years in teaching	2.684	0.298	1.636	0.161	Accept H_1
	Family business background	0.621	0.621	3.089	0.088	Accept H_1
	Entrepreneurial experience	0.471	0.471	2.286	0.140	Accept H_1
	Entrepreneurial education	0.277	0.277	1.305	0.262	Accept H_1
	Entrepreneurial training	0.041	0.041	0.188	0.667	Accept H_1

Based on the decision rule, the result of the analysis shows in Table 11 indicates that the human relations entrepreneurial competence of teachers does not statistically differ significantly. Hence, the null hypothesis 1 was accepted. This implies that the profile variables do not vary substantially in their human relations entrepreneurial competence. This is because the significance level provided in the SPSS result is greater than the alpha value (0.05). Kokemuller, N. (2018) refers to human relations as the interpersonal interactions of employees. Most managers' perspective on human relations is to create communication channels and systems that enable strong employee relationships. From an individual employee perspective, it refers to your ability to interact healthily with other people to build effective relationships.

Table 12 indicates the result of the analysis that technical, entrepreneurial competence of the respondents does not statistically differ significantly based on the decision rule. And so, the null hypothesis 1 was accepted. This is because the significance level provided it is greater than the alpha value 0.05, which implies that the profile variable does not significantly differ in their technical level of entrepreneurial competence. Technical competencies are abilities directly related to the type of training and the technical aptitude required to apply operational control. It also reflects the ability to understand and carry out a specific task, or series of functions, in the workplace. The importance of technical competence in the workplace often depends on the job role (Petersen, L., 2018).

Table 12 - ANOVA Result on Technical Entrepreneurial Competence

Dependent Variable	Grouping/Independent Variable	SS	MS	F	p-value	Decision
Technical Competence	Age	4.447	0.278	1.872	0.105	Accept H_1
	Sex	0.012	0.012	0.056	0.814	Accept H_1
	Years in teaching	2.221	0.247	1.247	0.315	Accept H_1
	Family business background	0.255	0.255	1.217	0.278	Accept H_1
	Entrepreneurial experience	0.029	0.029	0.136	0.715	Accept H_1
	Entrepreneurial education	0.242	0.242	1.149	0.292	Accept H_1
	Entrepreneurial training	0.248	0.248	1.179	0.286	Accept H_1

As displayed in table 13 below of the ANOVA result, it can be interpreted that there is a significant difference in the commitment level of entrepreneurial competence as to the entrepreneurial experience with a p-value at 0.04. This may entail that those with experience in entrepreneurship allow them to be more involved and motivated towards the entrepreneurial endeavor. Commitment is the link between employees experience with their organization.

According to Wainwright, B. (2018), employees who are committed to their organization generally feel a connection with their organization. Most of these employees tend to be more determined and engaged in their job, have relatively high productivity, and often proactive in offering their support.

Table 13 - ANOVA Result on Commitment Entrepreneurial Competence

Dependent Variable	Grouping/Independent Variable	SS	MS	F	p-value	Decision
Commitment Competence	Age	5.321	0.333	1.940	0.093	Accept H_1
	Sex	0.177	0.177	0.703	0.408	Accept H_1
	Years in teaching	1.360	0.151	0.528	0.840	Accept H_1
	Family business background	0.020	0.020	0.078	0.782	Accept H_1
	Entrepreneurial experience	1.882	1.882	9.481	0.004	Reject H_1
	Entrepreneurial education	0.013	0.013	0.051	0.823	Accept H_1
	Entrepreneurial training	0.165	0.165	0.655	0.424	Accept H_1

As shown in Table 14, the result of the analysis on the opportunity level of entrepreneurial competence of the respondents indicates no significant difference statistically based on the decision rule. And so, the null hypothesis 1 was accepted. Thus, the significance level provided it is greater than the alpha value 0.05, which implies that the profile variables do not significantly differ in their opportunity level of entrepreneurial competence among the respondents teaching entrepreneurship education.

Table 14 - ANOVA Result on Opportunity Entrepreneurial Competence

Dependent Variable	Grouping/Independent Variable	SS	MS	F	p-value	Decision
Opportunity Competence	Age	4.350	0.272	1.354	0.271	Accept H_1
	Sex	0.040	0.040	0.164	0.688	Accept H_1
	Years in teaching	1.890	0.210	0.858	0.573	Accept H_1
	Family business background	0.015	0.015	0.061	0.807	Accept H_1
	Entrepreneurial experience	0.471	0.471	2.065	0.160	Accept H_1
	Entrepreneurial education	0.102	0.102	0.428	0.518	Accept H_1
	Entrepreneurial training	0.010	0.010	0.043	0.838	Accept H_1

As one of the entrepreneurial competencies, opportunity competence is considered as at the heart of entrepreneurship research. The entrepreneurial process often starts with identifying the potential business ideas that could be further developed into a new product or service (Baggen et al., 2015). Opportunities are determined by the environment, whereas opportunities in the creation view are determined by the individual (Suddaby, Bruton, & Si, 2015).

Table 15 - ANOVA Result on Organizational Entrepreneurial Competence

Dependent Variable	Grouping/Independent Variable	SS	MS	F	p-value	Decision
Organizational Competence	Age	5.107	0.319	1.734	0.135	Accept H_1
	Sex	0.110	0.110	0.434	0.515	Accept H_1
	Years in teaching	3.360	0.373	1.838	0.113	Accept H_1
	Family business background	0.235	0.235	0.941	0.339	Accept H_1
	Entrepreneurial experience	0.118	0.118	0.464	0.501	Accept H_1
	Entrepreneurial education	0.013	0.013	0.051	0.823	Accept H_1
	Entrepreneurial training	0.165	0.165	0.655	0.424	Accept H_1

Table 15 indicates the result of the analysis that the organizational, entrepreneurial competence of the respondents does not statistically differ significantly based on the decision rule. And so, the null hypothesis 1 was accepted. This is because the significance level provided it is higher than the alpha value 0.05, which implies that the profile variables do not significantly differ in their opportunity level of entrepreneurial competence. Organizational competencies are necessary in the business in order to remain and excel in a competitive market. According to Satyendra (2018), it includes expected attitudes, behaviors, and skills, which lead to the organization's success and it relies greatly on the competencies of the workforces of the organization.

As shown in table 16 below, it is indicated that there is a significant difference in the level of strategic competence as to the years of teaching with a p-value at 0.042, possibly, the number of years in teaching may influence the ability to develop a clearly defined and focused vision. Since experience helps to develop the skills at both reasoning with a strategic purpose as well as making a visioning process. Also, there is also a significant

difference in strategic competence as to entrepreneurial education with a p-value at 0.040. This may be because strategic thinking enables a person to determine how to use resources most effectively and advance the company toward its objective, to do so, one must have knowledge or education regarding this matter.

Table 16 - ANOVA Result on Strategic Entrepreneurial Competence

Dependent Variable	Grouping/Independent Variable	SS	MS	F	p-value	Decision
Strategic Competence	Age	11.389	0.712	1.798	0.120	Accept H_1
	Sex	0.018	0.018	0.031	0.861	Accept H_1
	Years in teaching	8.576	0.953	2.397	0.042	Reject H_1
	Family business background	0.069	0.069	0.122	0.729	Accept H_1
	Entrepreneurial experience	1.882	1.882	3.710	0.063	Accept H_1
	Entrepreneurial education	2.278	2.278	4.601	0.040	Reject H_1
	Entrepreneurial training	0.026	0.026	0.047	0.830	Accept H_1

Strategic competencies develop people and organizations to take a stand and move in a highly active context that poses continually changing challenges to the realization of their aims. However, according to Wigboldus (2015), there is no fixed course of action that can be planned, because of the multiple uncertainties same as playing the game does mean knowing the rules of the game, but it is also the ability to apply and incorporate relevant experiences, the ability to adapt different scenarios and continually develop, and more.

Problem 4.2: Is there a significant difference in the level of utilization of teaching methods when grouped according to the profile variables?

Table 17 - ANOVA Result on Teaching Methods Utilization

Dependent Variable	Grouping/Independent Variable	SS	MS	F	p-value	Decision
Teaching Methods	Age	153.193	51.064	1.045	0.387	Accept H_2
	Sex	1.776	0.592	3.362	0.032	Reject H_2
	Years in teaching	143.795	47.932	1.403	0.261	Accept H_2
	Family business background	34.943	11.648	2.558	0.074	Accept H_2
	Entrepreneurial experience	2.703	0.901	4.686	0.008	Reject H_2
	Entrepreneurial education	0.816	0.272	1.061	0.380	Accept H_2
	Entrepreneurial training	1.156	0.385	2.116	0.119	Accept H_2

As shown, there is a significant difference in the teaching method level of utilization as to sex with a p-value at 0.032, this may indicate that male and female teachers have different methods in teaching the subject, and their sex may influence these differences. In addition to that, it is also indicated in the table that entrepreneurial experience statistically differs significantly with a p-value of 0.008. It may be because the experience acquired in the entrepreneurial endeavors provides a variety of ways in teaching the subject.

Problem 5: Is there a significant relationship between the entrepreneurial competence and teaching method?

Table 18 - Correlation Result on Entrepreneurial Competence and Teaching Methods

Entrepreneurial Competence	Teaching Methods		
	r - value	p - value	Decision
Conceptual	.811**	.000	Reject H_3
Human Relations	.777**	.000	Reject H_3
Technical	.850**	.000	Reject H_3
Commitment	.760**	.000	Reject H_3
Opportunity	.777**	.000	Reject H_3
Organizational	.777**	.000	Reject H_3
Strategic	.777**	.000	Reject H_3

Legend: Asterisk (**) indicates that correlation is significant relationship at 0.05 level.

In these results, the p-values for the correlation between entrepreneurial competencies and teaching method are less than the significance level of 0.05, which indicates that the correlation coefficients are significant. It also demonstrates that the competencies have a strong positive correlation with teaching methods, and technical level has the strongest correlation (r=0.850) among the variables. Since there is a strong linear relationship between the

variables and the relationship is positive, once the level of entrepreneurial competence increases, the level of utilization of teaching methods also increases.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The majority of the teachers handling entrepreneurship subject in senior high school had limited business background, experiences, and training on the subject taught. These indicate that there is a shortage of business teachers being hired to teach the subject, and so, the school administrators resort to non-business teachers to handle the said subject. As a result, the technical competence of the subject is lower compared to the rest of the entrepreneurship competencies. Better learning and development happens in a dynamic environment in which teachers has very high technical competence since they offer explicit, active instruction to students.

Entrepreneurship education mainly requires student engagement because of the complexity of the entrepreneurship process. Like other education, teaching methods have an essential role in entrepreneurship education. Its effectiveness is mainly related to the competence and knowledge of the teachers of the subject and their use of applicable variety of teaching methods in teaching the subject. As such, the level of the teachers' entrepreneurial competence is correlated with the utilization of the methods used in entrepreneurship education.

Teachers play a crucial role in enhancing students' achievement in schools. What teachers do in the classroom is critical to this process. The scope of this research offers educators a clear picture of the areas to improve to maximize the delivery in teaching entrepreneurship education. This may be used to recommend these competencies as the core around which to build teacher preparation, teacher hiring, teacher development, and teacher and school evaluations.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

To develop the technical competence of the teachers, an entrepreneurial competency development training should be implemented. The training should focus on the creation of business plans, based on the curriculum guides provided by the Department of Education for the said subject (see Appendix A). A unified training module must also be provided to make sure the consistency and uniformity in the delivery of instructions during the training sessions and of the lessons in the classroom. The teachers may also use this module as a guide in the conduct of classroom discussion in the said subject after the proposed training.

To make the training more meaningful, it is essential for the teachers to be closely monitored after the program to ensure that they are appropriately making use of the learned concept, knowledge, and skills. This will also reveal gray areas in the program and correct them in time. The result of this research may be used as a basis for the development of entrepreneurship teacher competency criteria that is very useful during the hiring process, job assignment, training plan, and evaluation.

Finally, because of recent implantation of K to 12 Basic Education, particularly with entrepreneurship education in the Philippines, one of this study's limitations was related to a small sample of teachers handling the subject in the division. Future studies could investigate a broader population and in a combination of teaching methods in this course. Examine this result in other courses could be another research.

REFERENCES

1. Adedeji, Babatunji & Rahman, Mohammad. (2018). Innovative Teaching Methods and Entrepreneurship Education: A Review of Literature. *Journal of Business Economics and Management*.
2. Ahmed, I., Nawaz, M. M., Ahmad, Z., Shaukat, M. Z., Usman, A., Rehman, W. U., & Ahmed, N. (2010). Determinants of students' entrepreneurial career intentions: Evidence from business graduates. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 15(2), 14-22."
3. Anderson, A. R., & Jack, S. L. (2008). Role typologies for enterprising education: the professional artisan? *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 15(2), 259–273. "
4. Arasti, Zahra & , Corresponding & Falavarjani, Mansoreh & Imanipour, Narges. (2012). A Study of Teaching Methods in Entrepreneurship Education for Graduate Students. *Higher Education Studies*. 2. 10.5539/hes.v2n1p2.
5. Baggen, Y., Mainert, J., Lans, T., Biemans, H. J. A., Greiff, S., & Mulder, M. (2015). Linking complex problem solving to opportunity identification competence within the context of entrepreneurship. *International Journal of Lifelong Education*, 34, 412–429. doi:10.1080/02601370.2015.1060029
6. Bennett, M. (2006). Business lecturers' perception of the nature of entrepreneurship, *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour & Research*, Vol. 12 No. 3, pp. 165-88.
7. Bird, B. 1995. Towards a theory of entrepreneurial competency. *Advances in Entrepreneurship, Firm Emergence and Growth*. 2, 51-72."
8. Bird, B.(2002). Learning Entrepreneurship Competencies: Directed Learning Approach, *International Journal of Entrepreneurship Education*. 1.pp. 203-227.
9. Boyatzis, R.E (1982). *The Competent Manager: A Model for Effective Performance*. New York: Willey."
10. Bradford, R. (2019). *Course and Direction: The Path to Strategic Success*. from <https://www.cssp.com/cd0808b/criticalstrategictthinkingskills/> Center for Simplified Strategic Planning, Inc

11. Capote, V., & Vedula-Dinagsao, A. (2015). Teachers' Entrepreneurial Competence and Knowledge of Business Management. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)* ISSN, 5. <https://doi.org/10.21275/16111601>
12. Colette Henry, Frances Hill, Claire Leitch, (2005) "Entrepreneurship education and training: can entrepreneurship be taught? Part I", *Education + Training*, Vol. 47 Issue: 2, pp.98-111, <https://doi.org/10.1108/00400910510586524>
13. Cruz, E.S. (2015, March 15). Phl needs K to 12 now. *The Philippine Star*. Retrieved from <http://www.philstar.com/opinion/2015/03/15/1433801/phl-needs-k-12-now>"
14. Dao-Anes (2015). Entrepreneurial Competencies of the Members of Universal Multi-purpose Cooperative. Benguet State University, La Trinidad, Benguet.
15. Deakins, D., Glancey, K., Menter, I. and Wyper, J. (2005), "Enterprise education: the role of the head teacher", *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, Vol. 1 No. 2, pp. 241-63."
16. Department of Education. (2017). K to 12 General Information. Retrieved from Department of Education website: <http://www.deped.gov.ph/k-to-12/faq>"
17. Department of Education. (2017, January 13). DepEd: K to 12 is for the triumph of Filipino learners. Retrieved from Department of Education website: <http://www.deped.gov.ph/pressreleases/deped-k-12-triumph-filipino-learners>"
18. Duval-Couetil, N. (2013). Assessing the impact of entrepreneurship education programs: Challenges and approaches. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 51(3), 394-409.
19. Elena Ruskovaara, Timo Pihkala, (2013) "Teachers implementing entrepreneurship education: classroom practices", *Education + Training*, Vol. 55 Issue: 2, pp.204-216, <https://doi.org/10.1108/00400911311304832>
20. European Commission (2011). Entrepreneurship Education: Enabling Teachers as a Critical Success Factor. A report on Teacher Education and Training to prepare teachers for the challenge of entrepreneurship education. Brussels.
21. European Commission. (2008). Entrepreneurship in higher education, especially within non-business studies. Directorate-General for Enterprise and Industry.
22. Fatoki, O. (2014). The entrepreneurial intention of undergraduate students in South Africa: The influences of entrepreneurship education and previous work experience. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(7), 294-299."
23. Fayolle, A. and Gailly, B. (2008). From craft to science: Teaching models and learning processes in entrepreneurship education. *Journal of European Industrial Training*, vol. 32, no.7, pp. 569 -593.
24. Fayolle, A., Gailly, B., & Lassas-Clerc, N. (2006). Assessing the impact of entrepreneurship education programmes: a new methodology. *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 30(9), 701-720. "
25. Fiet, J. (2000a). The theoretical side of teaching entrepreneurship. *Journal of Business Venturing*. 16. 1-24. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0883-9026\(99\)00041-5](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0883-9026(99)00041-5)
26. Gartner, W.B., (2008) "Variations in entrepreneurship", *Small Business Economics*, Vol.3 No.4, pp.351-61.
27. Gatchalian, MLB (2010). An In-depth Analysis of the Entrepreneurship Education in the Philippines: An Initiative Towards the Development of a Framework for a Professional Teaching Competency Program for Entrepreneurship Educators. *Internal Journal of Research and Review*, Vol.5.
28. Gautam, Manish. (2015). Entrepreneurship Education: Concept, Characteristics and Implications for Teacher Education. *Shaikshik Parisamvad*. 5. 21-35.
29. Gibb, A. 2011. Concepts into practice: meeting the development of entrepreneurship educators around an innovative paradigm: The case of the International Entrepreneurship Educators' Programme (IEEP). *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour & Research*, 17, 146-165
30. Hair, J., Black, W., Babin, B., & Anderson, R. (2010). *Multivariate Data Analysis*. Upper Saddle River.
31. Hindle, K. (2007). Teaching entrepreneurship at university : from the wrong building "We are different: a case study of entrepreneurship education in Malaysia" to the right philosophy. In *Handbook of research in entrepreneurship education*, 1 (pp. 104-126)."
32. Katariina Peltonen, (2015) "How can teachers' entrepreneurial competences be developed? A collaborative learning perspective", *Education Training*, Vol. 57 Issue: 5, pp.492-511, <https://doi.org/10.1108/ET-03-2014-0033>
33. Kissi, Ernest & Somiah, Matthew & K. Samuel, Ansah. (2015). Towards Entrepreneurial Learning Competencies: The Perspective of Built Environment Students. *Higher Education Studies*. 5. 10.5539/hes.v5n1p20.
34. Komarkova, I., Conrads, J., & Collado, A. (2015). Entrepreneurship competence: An overview of existing concepts, policies and initiatives - final report. JRC Science and Policy Reports. <https://doi.org/10.2791/067979>
35. Kumar Gautam, M., Scholar, R., & Kumar Singh, S. (2015). Entrepreneurship Education: concept, characteristics and implications for teacher education. *An International Journal of Education) SPIJE*.
36. Kütüm, M., Kallaste, M., Venesaar, U., & Kiis, A. (2014). Entrepreneurship education at university level and students' entrepreneurial intentions. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 110, 658-668.

37. Lacap, Jean Paolo. (2017). Senior High School Students' Entrepreneurial Inclination: The Case of Accountancy, Business, and Management Track Students in Pampanga, Philippines. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Business*. 5. 37-49.
38. Lans, T., & Gulikers, J. (2018, October 03). Handbook of Research in Entrepreneurship Education, Volume 3. Retrieved from <https://www.elgaronline.com/view/9781848440968.00011.xml>
39. LI, Xiang. Entrepreneurial Competencies as an Entrepreneurial Distinctive: An Examination of the Competency Approach in Defining Entrepreneurs. (2009). Dissertations and Theses Collection (Open Access).
40. Man, T., Lau, T. and Chan, K.F. (2002). The competitiveness of small and medium enterprises. a conceptualisation with focus on entrepreneurial competencies. *Journal of Business Venturing*, Vol. 17 No.2, pp.123-142."
41. Maresch, D., Harms, R., Kailer, N., & Wimmer-Wurm, B. (2016). The impact of entrepreneurship education on the entrepreneurial intention of students in science and engineering versus business studies university programs. *Technological forecasting and social change*, 104, 172-179.
42. McClelland, D. C. 1987. Characteristics of successful entrepreneurs, *Journal of Creative Behavior*. 21(1), 18-21. pp.219-233."
43. Mitchelmore, S., & Rowley, J. (2010). Entrepreneurial competencies: a literature review and development agenda. *International journal of entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 16(2), 92-111.
44. Mohd Zahari Ismail, Syed Zamberi Ahmad, (2013) "Entrepreneurship education: an insight from Malaysian polytechnics", *Journal of Chinese Entrepreneurship*, Vol.5 Issue: 2, pp.144-160, <https://doi.org/10.1108/JCE-02-2013-0003>
45. MSME Statistics. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.dti.gov.ph/businesses/msmes/msme-resources/msme-statistics>
46. Mwasalwiba, E. S. (2010). Entrepreneurship education: a review of its objectives, teaching methods, and impact indicators. *Education+Training*, Vol. 52 Iss. 1 pp. 20 – 47, doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/00400911011017663>
47. Neck, H.M. and Greene, P.G. (2011), "Entrepreneurship Education: Known worlds and new frontiers", *Journal of Small Business Management*, Vol. 49 No.1, pp. 55-70."
48. Ogonnia, N. (2016). The imperatives of teaching methods in improving the entrepreneurial competencies of business education students in universities in south east and south south states of Nigeria. *British Journal of Education*, 4 (13), 59-69.
49. Pfeifer, S., Šarlija, N., & Zekić Sušac, M. (2016). Shaping the Entrepreneurial Mindset: Entrepreneurial Intentions of Business Students in Croatia. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 54(1), 102-117.
50. Pihie, Z. A. L., & Bagheri, A. (2011). Teachers' and students' entrepreneurial self-efficacy: Implication for effective teaching practices. In *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.11.340>
51. Pittaway, L., & Cope, J. (2007). Entrepreneurship Education A Systematic Review of the Evidence. *International Small Business Journal*, 25(5), 479–510.
52. Ruskovaara, E., & Pihkala, T. (2013). Teachers implementing entrepreneurship education: Classroom practices. *Education and Training*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00400911311304832>
53. Seikkula-Leino, J. (2008), "Advancing entrepreneurship education in the Finnish basic education the prospect of developing local curricula", in Fayolle, A. and Kyro, P. (Eds), *The Dynamics between Entrepreneurship, Environment and Education*, Edward Elgar, Cheltenham, pp. 168-90."
54. Sirelkhatim, F., & Gangi, Y. (2015). Entrepreneurship education: A systematic literature review of curricula contents and teaching methods. *Cogent Business and Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2015.1052034>
55. Solomon, G. (2007), "An examination of entrepreneurship education in the United States", *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, Vol. 14 No. 2, pp.168-82."
56. Stare, J., & Klun, M. (2016). Higher Education And Entrepreneurial Competencies For Students. *INTED2016 Proceedings*. doi:10.21125/inted.2016.1191
57. Suddaby, R., Bruton, G. D., & Si, S. X. (2015). Entrepreneurship through a qualitative lens: Insights on the construction and/or discovery of entrepreneurial opportunity. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 30, 1–10.
58. Tschannen-Moran, M. and D. Johnson, 2011. Exploring literacy teachers' self-efficacy beliefs: Potential sources at play. *Teach. Teach. Educ.*
59. UNESCO/ILO 2006, *Global Towards an Entrepreneurial culture for the twenty-first Century*. (2006)
60. Velasco, A. (2013). Entrepreneurship Education in the Philippines. *DLSU Business & Economics Review*, 22(2). Retrieved from <http://ejournals.ph/form/cite.php?id=6456>
61. Z.A. Lope Pihie and A. Bagheri, 2011. Are Teachers Qualified to Teach Entrepreneurship? Analysis of Entrepreneurial Attitude and Self-efficacy. *Journal of Applied Sciences*, 11: 3308-3314.
62. Zappe, S. E., Hochstedt, K. S., & Kisenwether, E. C. (2013). Faculty beliefs of Entrepreneurship and design education: An exploratory study comparing entrepreneurship and design faculty. *Journal of Engineering Entrepreneurship*.

Appendix A

Teachers' Training Curriculum Overview

A. Purpose

To gain an understanding of the basic concepts of Entrepreneurship, how their application builds an organization's capacity overall and to develop entrepreneurial competencies of the participants.

B. Audience

Senior High School Teachers in the Department of Education – Surigao del Norte Division handling Entrepreneurship subjects.

C. Learning Objectives

By the end of the workshop, participants will:

1. Demonstrate knowledge of key Entrepreneurship concepts and principles.
2. Understand how to develop entrepreneurial competencies to support their teaching strategies.
3. Know how to recognize and understand a potential market and the importance of marketing mix in marketing strategy development and 4Ms of operation.
4. Demonstrates understanding of concepts, underlying principles, and processes of developing a business plan.
5. Manifest understanding of starting and operating a simple business.

D. Curriculum

This curriculum includes 10 sessions and is based on the research paper's survey analysis to obtain feedback and tailor the workshop to meet participants' needs. A variety of methodologies is used—case studies, scenarios, games and role plays—to illustrate and develop the participants' entrepreneurial competencies. Participants work primarily in small groups of approximately four to six people to allow greater participation and feedback.

A session guide will be developed for facilitators to use to conduct this training. For each session of the workshop, the guide includes the session title, objectives, content overview with suggested format and timing for each activity within a session, as well as any advance preparation and supplies needed to carry out the session. The guide also includes notes and specific instructions to guide facilitators to carry out all activities for each of the sessions.

SESSION	TRAINING CONTENT
1	The Role of Creativity in Entrepreneurship
2	Recognizing and Understanding the Market
3	Planning the Enterprise
4	Marketing Mix
5	Marketing Plan
6	The 4Ms of Operations
7	Production Plan
8	Management and Organization Plan
9	Financial Plan
10	Implement the Business Plan

E. Facilitator

It is suggested that a workshop for 35 participants be conducted by at least five facilitators. Facilitators should have experiences in teaching entrepreneurship, implementation of business plans, owns a business, and should familiarize themselves with the training materials in advance.

F. Agenda

A suggested agenda for a three-day workshop is in Appendix A; however, organizers may want to consider expanding it to four days by adding time to the sessions. The proposed agenda may also be revised as needed based on discussions with participating organizations. The curriculum is formatted in such a way so that sessions can be chosen that applicable to the organizations.

G. Materials

Participants should receive a packet containing materials for their use during and post training. The handouts in Appendix B may be distributed at the appropriate session or at the beginning of the workshop.

H. Preparation

The results and analysis of the research paper should be the basis to gauge participants' interests and needs; the activities in this workshop should be based on the results of the survey. Workshop planners and facilitators should review the materials in each session to determine all the materials they will need. PowerPoint slides should contain a

great deal of important information and complement the use of this guide; once facilitators are familiar with the content, the slides can be edited and shortened to improve presentation.